

Release Notes 2022-08-01 : : I was going to drop vitamin D as a topic once I got the controversy note draft [18] out but this trial design was too funny and important to ignore. I won't have much time in next few days so releasing this today :) I'm interested in emulsifiers and absorption aids, currently have benzoate results queued up, like sorbitol but the anti-pathogen properties of dyes may be of larger significance. Once again I'm using developmental bibliography formatting code. It is not all that pretty but I'm finding wierd quirks as different sites reformat the submission so it is useful for debugging. The links should be live for now but the bibliography is supposed to preserve information if the links change. It is part of the TooBib [21] work which also should have turned the LinkedIn footnotes into better citations but they recently changed their page layout and I did not get back to this.

This work addresses a controversial topic and likely advances one or more viewpoints that are not well accepted in an attempt to resolve confusion. The reader is assumed familiar with the related literature and controversial issues and in any case should seek additional input from sources the reader trusts likely with differing opinions. For information and thought only not intended for any particular purpose. Caveat Emptor

I am not a veterinarian or a doctor or health care professional and this is not particular advice for any given situation. Read the disclaimers in the appendicies or text, take them seriously and take prudent steps to evaluate this information.

This is a draft and has not been peer reviewed or completely proof read but released in some state where it seems worthwhile given time or other constraints. Typographical errors are quite likely particularly in manually entered numbers. This work may include output from software which has not been fully debugged. For information only, not for use for any particular purpose see fuller disclaimers in the text. Caveat Emptor.

Live and Let Dye: A Confounding Factor in Vitamin D Data, Covid-19 Treatments and Everything Else ?

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(Dated: August 1, 2022)

Foods, drugs, and cosmetics are often formulated with ingredients to enhance the performance of active components. These components may improve physical properties, resistance to storage and environment, and appeal to consumers. They may be glibly considered inert in the absence of the active ingredients but this assumption needs to be considered when designing trials ostensibly evaluating the "active" ingredient. Dyes and absorption enhancers are two classes of common ingredients that may be active and confound the study of the intended ingredient. Dyes may have anti-pathogen properties that improve results in populations with significant infection rates among other effects. Absorption enhancers may be promiscuous or otherwise change nutrient profiles for host and other organisms beyond just the active ingredient similarly creating benefits or even detriment for afflicted patients. One important point is that no "thing" does just one thing but ingredients intended for these purposes may confound isolation of active ingredient effects. This is considered in the case of vitamin D formulations and possible interference in assessing it for covid-19 but the problem is pervasive.

I was recently exploring vitamin D controversies [18]. A related discussion on social media¹ brought to my attention a study in which vitamin D supplementation was shown to improve outcomes in covid-19 patients [24]. Results with vitamin D interventions for covid-19 have been mixed although some correlations or associations appear robust [18] so successful intervention trials create some curiosity. The authors appear to be giving Hidroferol to a treatment group but there is no indication of a placebo containing an identical vehicle- I may have missed it but this situation is quite common so worth consideration in any case. According to [3],

"Hidroferol contains ethanol, sorbitol (E-420) and sunset yellow (E-110)."

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¹ <https://www.linkedin.com/in/jon-bergstrom-ph-d-61674a16/> <https://www.linkedin.com/in/antonio-d-avolio-6b208240> https://www.linkedin.com/posts/antonio-d-avolio-6b208240_impaired-vitamin-d-metabolism-in-hospitalized-activity-6957581592735199232-Pi [https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6957581592735199232?commentUrn=urn:li:comment:\(activity:A6957581592735199232,6958075248181211137\)](https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6957581592735199232?commentUrn=urn:li:comment:(activity:A6957581592735199232,6958075248181211137)),

While ethanol is listed as "1 percent" the total amounts of the other components is unclear. In this strength the vitamin D content is 266mcg and I would guess around 500mg or so for the vehicle. With no vehicle-only control group, the trial implicitly assumes that it is inert but a quick look at the assumption raises doubts about its role in this application. The individual components themselves are suspicious but even less predictable in combination.

Sorbitol itself is probably included to aid uptake but it is not selective for vitamin D. It has a history going back to at least 1959 as an arguable aid to B-12 absorption [11] [25], iron absorption [2], and is currently a concern for decreasing absorption of pharmaceuticals [13]. Even small amounts of sorbitol had to be suspected of improving availability of many nutrients especially with its ability to participate in deep eutectic solvent systems [9]. Sorbitol as a significant fraction of feed has been shown to improve livestock response to feed [10] at least in some animals [27]. Inconsistent effects could rely upon the mitigation or exacerbation of some unanticipated sporadic problem such as pathogen infection [5] or nutrient malabsorption. Sorbitol alone may even have activity similar to vitamin D as one work suggests sugars are associated with osteopetrosis and sorbitol has some calcium related functions [32].

Food dyes are a continuing source of safety controversy but often considered "inert" if they are not overtly dangerous. However, they typically have significant chemistry and biological activity particularly among the common azo dyes with planar ring systems. For example, sulfonated azo dyes as well as doxycycline were found to be selective inhibitors of "Suppressor of T cell receptor Signaling" in an interaction assisted by the rings of tryptophan or tyrosine [38]. Allergic reactions to drugs are often traced to the dyes [31]. It is so common that one case report identified it as a cause of serial adverse reactions to calcium supplements, carbamazepine, topiramate, phenytoin, levetiracetam after which the excipients were suspected and confirmed as an allergy to sunset yellow [15]. Allergic reactions reflect immune modulation and would have to be considered in the host response to pathogens.

Many dyes types have antibiotic effects. Acridine for example is a decent antibiotic skeleton [35]. In 2018, Meng et al demonstrated activity against Human Enterovirus 71 in vitro and in mice with a variety of sulfonated azo dyes, including sunset yellow, via a several mechanisms [22]. Later work in 2021 suggested related dyes could increase infectivity [23]. Direct action of dyes on SARS-Cov-2 was investigated soon after it was identified. For example, diazo dye docking studies with SARS-Cov-2 [6] and a study of small molecule inhibitors directed only at SARS-Cov-2 Spike:ACE2 interaction [8] were described. The latter uses sunset yellow (FD and C Yellow 6) as a "negative control" on entry inhibition although it may show some effects below $100\mu M$ (figure 8 [8]). However, there is no reason to believe that "entry inhibition" is the only way it could have clinical relevance. Methylene blue has been directly investigated as an SARS-Cov-2 therapeutic [12] [14] with many possible virus and host directed mechanisms hypothesized.

Azo dyes are common in food and drugs with sunset yellow itself being quite common in drugs that may be used against SARS-Cov-2. At least one formulation of azutrhomycin contains FD&C Yellow 6 [1] The amount of dye in commercial products such as drugs and supplements is not public but some measurements have been made and 1mg/tablet would not be unrealistic [16]. Its worth noting however that significant amounts may be in common snacks [29] which should effect all arms equally but may vary significantly with age and culture. Sunset yellow has a molecular weight of 452.4. One milligram is then about 2.2 micromoles. Dissolved in 1 liter of stomach contents then micromolar concentrations may be transiently possible with localized higher ones. There is some possibility that at lower concentrations sunset yellow could have impact on relevant pathogens. The work on in vitro and in mice azo dye experiments with EV-71 indicated that E-151 (Brilliant Black) inhibitory concentrations were around , " $2.39\mu M$ to $28.12\mu M$, whereas its 50% cytotoxic concentration was $1,870\mu M$ ", leading the authors to speculate that 1-5mg/kg/day of E-151 may have significant clinical benefit [22]. Mice receiving 200mg/kg/day uniformly survive an EV-71 challenge. Sunset yellow had a higher inhibitory concentration under these conditions and was not investigated as thoroughly as the superlative dyes.

Covid-19 is generally attributed to or defined by SARS-Cov-2. However, interactions with other pathogens have been described. Debate over the efficacy of Ivermectin identified efficacy against covid-19 due to elimination of parasites as expected of the drug with no efficacy "where strongyloidiasis was not endemic" [7]. It is usually considered as a respiratory disease although a GI component exists [37] and is currently of unknown significance [28] [36]. Bloodstream infections with GI organisms may be one concern [33]. The fact that one formulation component had activity against any GI pathogen is itself cause for interest. Direct activity against any part of the SARS-Cov-2 lifecycle is not necessary to change a clinical outcome. Therefore, it is difficult to be confident that any clinical response is due to the intended drug or an excipient or some interaction. covid-19 also has steep robust age-severity curve. As chronological age per se is not likely a factor, age-related host changes have to be suspected as mediators. These have variously been considered as immunological and nutritional changes[20]. Observed or suspected changes to both may occur from the combination of ingredients included discussed here. Pathogen virulence and clinical relevance may be an inducible phenotype so changes in nutrient availability could have a clinical impact.

Mitigation of a subclinical risk factor for severe covid-19 is still important to the patient but improvement will only be observed in the population with this unseen risk factor. Infectious causes of other diseases such as the earlier case of ulcer [30] and more recently Alzheimer's Disease [4] [34] are becoming better accepted. Awareness of virulence

modulation from components such as this may help resolve contemporary debates and lead to better solutions. The combination of dye with an uptake modifier is probably not safely assumed to be neutral towards pathogens or the patient's immune status. Indeed, modified uptake due to sorbitol may alter any IC_{50} significantly.

If you absolutely insist that "X is a Y and does Z" then it is easy to miss problems like this (unpublished personal notes [19]) . However, consideration of all aspects of each ingredient may avoid misleading interpretations. In any case, it is important to consider the vehicle as potentially live and consider it as at least one control arm. This may be a particular problem with vitamin D but if dyes and other formulation components are active against pathogens it could be much more widespread. Apparent benefit would only be seen in populations with a susceptible clinically relevant organism or a specific immune status leading to inconsistent and confusing results.

Nutrient uptake, particularly of lipophilic nutrients or those with variable solubility and stability may be an unappreciated issue with aging. Particular components that get around those problems may be covert contributors to clinical effects. Sorbitol and dye may be one combination but I have also explored benzoate and silver for uptake and anti-pathogen effects [17]. It is possible that unappreciated interactions in natural food are also important.

I had earlier thought that the better controlled vitamin D trials were less successful and this is an example with questionable control but one that can be cited as a vitamin D success. Careful review of clinical trials for placebo among other issues may clarify roles for confounding formulation components.

Placebo matters and " a p-value is no substitute for a brain." [26]

FIG. 1: Structure of Sunset Yellow or FD and C yellow 6

1. SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION

1.1. Computer Code

2. BIBLIOGRAPHY

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1. Pubmed eutils facilities and the basic research it provides.
2. Free software including Linux, R, LaTeX etc.
3. Thanks everyone who contributed incidental support.

Appendix A: Statement of Conflicts

No specific funding was used in this effort and there are no relationships with others that could create a conflict of interest. I would like to develop these ideas further and have obvious bias towards making them appear successful. Barbara Cade, the dog owner, has worked in the pet food industry but this does not likely create a conflict. We have no interest in the makers of any of the products named in this work.

Appendix B: About the Authors and Facility

This work was performed at a dog rescue run by Barbara Cade and housed in rural Georgia. The author of this report ,Mike Marchywka, has a background in electrical engineering and has done extensive research using free online literature sources. I hope to find additional people interested in critically examining the results and verify that they can be reproduced effectively to treat other dogs.

Appendix C: Symbols, Abbreviations and Colloquialisms

TERM definition and meaning

Appendix D: General caveats and disclaimer

This document was created in the hope it will be interesting to someone including me by providing information about some topic that may include personal experience or a literature review or description of a speculative theory or idea. There is no assurance that the content of this work will be useful for any particular purpose.

All statements in this document were true to the best of my knowledge at the time they were made and every attempt is made to assure they are not misleading or confusing. However, information provided by others and observations that can be manipulated by unknown causes ("gaslighting") may be misleading. Any use of this information should be preceded by validation including replication where feasible. Errors may enter into the final work at every step from conception and research to final editing.

Documents labelled "NOTES" or "not public" contain substantial informal or speculative content that may be terse and poorly edited or even sarcastic or profane. Documents labelled as "public" have generally been edited to be more coherent but probably have not been reviewed or proof read.

Generally non-public documents are labelled as such to avoid confusion and embarassment and should be read with that understanding.

Appendix E: Citing this as a tech report or white paper

Note: This is mostly manually entered and not assured to be error free.
This is tech report MJM-2022-011.

Version	Date	Comments
0.01	2022-07-28	Create from empty.tex template
-	August 1, 2022	version 0.50 MJM-2022-011
1.0	20xx-xx-xx	First revision for distribution

Released versions,
build script needs to include empty releases.tex

Version	Date	URL

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run-date ="August 1, 2022" ,
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author ="Mike J Marchywka " ,
type ="techreport" ,
name ="marchywka-MJM-2022-011-0.50 " ,
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Supporting files. Note that some dates,sizes, and md5's will change as this is rebuilt.

This really needs to include the data analysis code but right now it is auto generated picking up things from prior build in many cases

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